

Oesophagostomy in Large Animal

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Abstract

The oesophagostomy is the surgical operation. It helps for restore the normal function of oesophagus. Otherwise, it leads to anorexia, aspiration pneumonia and other disorder in oesophageal tracts. It directly affects the productive performance and also affects the lifespan of animals.

Keywords: Oesophagus, coughing, aspiration pneumonia

Introduction

Oesophagostomy

Indications

Oesophageal obstruction, oesophageal diverticulum, oesophageal stenosis, oesophageal neoplasia etc. are the common indications of oesophagotomy.

Surgical Anatomy

The bovine oesophagus is 75-105 cm long Musculo membranous cylindrical tube, divided into cervical, thoracic and a very small abdominal part, extending from the pharynx to the cardia. Because the rumen is closely related to the diaphragm, no appreciable intraabdominal portion of the oesophagus exists. In the Cervical region proximal third of oesophagus is dorsal to the trachea till about the level of 3rd or 4th cervical vertebrae while the rest of the part deviates to the left and lies lateral to trachea up to the thoracic inlet. In the thoracic region, it is again median in position and enters the abdominal cavity through the hiatus oesophgi at the level of the eighth or ninth

intercostals space. It courses in the mediastinum, passing dorsal to the base of the heart and tracheal bifurcation. Structures that accompany the cervical oesophagus include the trachea and recurrent laryngeal nerve ventromedially, longus coli muscle dorsally, tracheal lymphatic trunk, deep cervical lymph nodes and carotid sheath containing common carotid artery, vagosympathetic trunk, internal jugular vein laterally. In the caudal mediastinum, the oesophagus is adjacent to the dorsal and ventral trunks of the vagus nerve. Dorsally, it is in proximity to the large caudal mediastinal lymph nodes. The oesophageal wall is thicker in the cervical part as

compared to the thoracic part. In the cervical region, its lumen narrows down at the junction of middle and distal third but again it widens slowly.

The oesophagus comprises of four layers that include the outer adventitial layer, muscular layers, submucosa and a thick mucosal layer that is thrown into longitudinal folds when empty. In the thoracic oesophagus the adventitial layer is replaced by a serosal covering, which is formed by the mediastinal pleura. In ruminants, except at the cranial and caudal ends, the tunica muscularis comprises the outer and inner spiral layers of striated muscle fibers that run throughout the length of the oesophagus. At the cranial and caudal ends, the inner muscle layer consists of circular fibers, whereas the outer layer consists of longitudinal fibers. Blood supply is from the cranial thyroid, common carotid and bronchoesophageal arteries. Nerve supply is from the branches of the vagus, sympathetic and recurrent laryngeal nerves.

Oesophageal Obstruction in Large Animals

Incidence The site of obstruction may be cervical or intrathoracic. The anterior end of the oesophagus behind the pharynx and the portion of the oesophagus situated between the first pair of ribs (i.e., at the entrance into thorax) are two common seats of obstruction in all species. The posterior third of the oesophagus is narrow in the horse ("funnel shaped") and therefore obstruction in the posterior part of the oesophagus is common in this species. The lumen of the oesophagus of cattle is narrower at its anterior end ("trumpet shaped") and therefore postpharyngeal obstructions are common in cattle.

Oesophageal obstruction is of infrequent occurrence in ruminants. It results from incomplete mastication and rapid ingestion. Cattle produce large quantities of saliva, which makes a smooth- skinned potato or apple difficult to masticate, so it can slip into the pharynx and esophagus.

Intraluminal blockade (choke) may occur due to vegetables (sources of obstruction include cabbage, beets, turnips, and ears of corn), fruits (large size lemon or apple), phytobezoars, tricobezoars and various foreign bodies, at times impacted dry feed. Extraluminal causes; large perioesophageal abscess, enlarged mediastinal lymph nodes and tumours, may also lead to partial obstruction of lumen of oesophagus due to pressure.

Clinical signs: Swelling in the ventral neck region and inability of the animal to swallow feed and water. There is salivation, tongue protrusion, and extension of the head and neck. The animal may be dehydrated and anxious. The patient remains thirsty and makes attempt to drink water which often returns back through the nostrils carrying food particles with it. Severe tympany occurs only if the obstruction is complete. If the obstruction persists for a longer duration and treatment is delayed, pressure necrosis of the mucosa may lead to perforation. Regurgitation may cause cough and aspiration pneumonia.

Diagnosis: Based on history, clinical signs and physical examination. After rabies has been ruled out, clinical examination is done. Obstruction in cervical region is easily palpated. When in doubt or if the thoracic oesophagus is involved, a probang or a stomach tube may be passed into the oesophagus to locate the probable site of obstruction.

Plain radiographs can show esophageal distention with gas or deviation of the esophagus. Contrast studies (barium swallow 50 to 150 ml) helpful to locate the site of obstruction but also for differential diagnosis of oesophageal diverticulum, stenosis or dilatation.

Esophagoscopy Esophagoscopy is indicated to help localize an obstruction, identify obstructing material, and assess damage to the esophagus, especially when the problem has been resolved. A 2- or 3-m flexible fiberoptic endoscope permits evaluation of the entire esophagus in most animals.

Treatment: The initial treatment of choke is aimed at resolving the ruminal tympany, by using a needle attached to a suction apparatus. Alternatively, a small trocar or cannula can be used to decompress the rumen. The treatment for choke can be categorized as conservative and surgical.

Conservative treatment is aimed at reducing the esophageal spasm and to dislodge the obstruction by external or internal manipulations. Xylazine (xylazine @ 01-.02 mg/kg/IV) can be used for both mild sedation of the animal and relaxation of the esophagus.

Once spasm is controlled and some degree of relaxation is achieved, it might be possible to clear the cervical obstruction by placing the thumb or fingers distal to the foreign body and

gradually forcing it upwards until it reaches the pharynx. Once the foreign body reaches the proximal esophagus, it may be possible to grasp the foreign object with the help of a mouth speculum and by pulling the tongue out of the oral cavity.

The thoracic esophagus widens slightly, making it possible to use a smooth stomach tube to advance some distal thoracic obstructions (mass is a round object) into the rumen where foreign materials can be retrieved via rumenotomy.

Along with these conservative treatments, animal must receive fluid therapy. The animal is often dehydrated and may be anxious or very agitated. Cattle lose tremendous quantities of saliva, which contains a large amount of bicarbonate; therefore cattle often develop metabolic acidosis with an esophageal obstruction.

Surgical treatment is indicated if conservative therapy fails.

Anaesthesia and Control Sedation and local infiltration at the site is sometimes adequate for cervical oesophagotomy in standing position or right lateral recumbency. General anaesthesia and positive pressure ventilation are essential for a thoracic oesophagotomy.

Site of Incision The incision site is along the superior or inferior border of jugular furrow close to the level of obstruction on the left side of the neck for cervical oesophagotomy. A left-sided rib resection (eighth rib) is usually performed for the thoracic oesophagotomy.

Surgical Procedure A lateral or ventrolateral approach is typically described for performing a cervical oesophagotomy. As the oesophagus is normally a flaccid tube that is difficult to recognise among the cervical muscles, it must be made visible by inserting a stomach tube up to the level of the obstruction prior to anaesthesia. The neck is prepared for aseptic surgery. An incision about 3-4 inches long is made along the superior or inferior border of left jugular furrow cutting through the skin and cervical cutaneous fascia. The oesophagus can be approached either between the trachea and sternocephalicus muscle, or between this muscle and the jugular vein. The oesophagus is recognized by its characteristic pink colour. After exposing the oesophagus, attempt should be made to push the obstructing mass, by direct manipulation towards the pharynx. If the attempt fails oesophagotomy is done.

The oesophagus is occluded either by placing a tape around it or by atraumatic clamps placed proximal and distal to the foreign body. The affected area is isolated from the surgical field using moist sponges. The wall of the oesophagus is incised longitudinally over the desired length cranial or caudal to the obstruction to get into the lumen and the obstruction is relieved.

Primary closure is recommended if the oesophageal wall has a normal appearance. If considerable dead space exists, a closed suction drain is advised for the first 48-72 hours. If the oesophageal wall is compromised, it should be allowed to heal by second intention with daily wound care. Primary oesophageal closure involves a 2-layer technique. First layer, the mucosa and submucosa are closed together in either a simple continuous or simple interrupted pattern. A synthetic absorbable (e.g., polyglactin-910, polydioxanone or polyglyconate) suture material is preferred. It is recommended the knots be tied within the oesophageal lumen to prevent contamination of the wound by ingesta migrating along suture tracts. Second layer, the muscular layer can be closed by using either an absorbable or nonabsorbable noncapillary suture with a simple interrupted or mattress pattern including surrounding fascia to strengthen the suture line. Skin is closed in a routine manner. In rare cases, when a foreign body is lodged at the cardia, rumenotomy may be done and a hand is introduced into the cardia to retrieve it.

Post-operative Care Food and water are withheld and adequate fluid therapy is given for several days; and soft foods must follow until healing is complete. Proper wound care, a course of antibiotics and anti-inflammatory medication is recommended.

Complications Possible complications include wound dehiscence resulting in fistula, and stenosis of oesophagus due to scar formation.

In case the foreign body is lodged at the cardia, rumenotomy may be done and a hand is introduced into the cardia to retrieve it.

Special Considerations Unfortunately, oesophageal surgery in any species is fraught with complications. Most of the oesophagus does not have a serosal covering, which is important in forming a fibrin seal. Furthermore, the esophageal lumen is not clean; constant movement occurs during swallowing, and its location causes tension on any suture line. The proximity of the recurrent laryngeal nerve to the oesophagus can have deleterious effects on manipulations. Once the muscular coat is incised, the oesophagus separates into two layers: the elastic inner layer, which is composed of mucosa and submucosa, and the outer muscular layer and adventitia. The inner layer provides the greatest tensile strength during oesophageal closure. Preservation of blood supply, aseptic technique, apposition of tissues without tension, and appropriate perioperative management are essential for a successful outcome.

Esophageal Diverticulum

It is the second most common esophageal disorder in the bovine. Diverticulum is a sac like protrusion of the oesophageal mucosa through a defect in the muscle layer. Diverticulum may occur due to pulsion or traction. Traction (true) diverticula results from contraction of periesophageal fibrous scar tissue, often secondary to a wound or previous surgery. Pulsion (false) diverticula results from protrusion of mucosa and submucosa through a defect in the esophageal musculature. Most of the diverticulum involve middle or distal cervical oesophagus. **The clinical signs** are similar to oesophageal obstruction. The animal may be able to swallow liquids. Solid's food is regurgitated. Coughing, salivation, and ruminal distention are typical. The diverticulum may enlarge over time and become evident as a large swelling in the neck, which results in dysphagia or choke.

Diagnosis is based on clinical and radiographic examination. Contrast radiographs with a barium swallow confirm the diagnosis.

Treatment includes surgical exposure of the oesophagus and resection of the diverticulum. Closure of wound and postoperative care is similar to oesophagotomy procedure.

Esophageal stenosis

Oesophagitis due to any cause can lead to stenosis of oesophagus. Injuries due to faulty introduction of a probang, post operative complication of oesophagotomy, cause stenosis. The clinical signs progress slowly and are similar to that of partial obstruction of the oesophagus. Diagnosis may be confirmed after contrast radiography with barium swallow.

If a small part of oesophagus is involved, resection of that part and end to end anastomosis may be done. In simple ring-shaped stenosis, the oesophagus is exposed and longitudinal incision over the stenosed part is given to include some normal oesophagus proximally and distally. Tissue forceps or stay sutures are applied one centimeter away on either side of the middle of the line of incision and drawn away to convert a longitudinal incision into a transverse one. The oesophagus is then sutured in this transverse position.

Esophagomyotomy

Oesophagomyotomy to dilate the lumen has not proved satisfactory in ruminants. Esophagomyotomy is indicated for an esophageal stricture that involves only the muscularis and adventitia. A stomach tube is positioned before surgery. The esophagus is approached and gently freed from surrounding tissues, and the structured area is identified. One or more longitudinal incisions are made in the esophageal musculature without incising the mucosa. The myotomy may or may not be sutured. The remainder of the surgical incision is closed and drained in a routine manner.

Oesophageal wounds and fistula

The wounds may lead to stenosis. Forceful introduction of a probang, trauma from outside or due to ingestion of foreign bodies may cause perforation and rupture of oesophagus. This results in subcutaneous emphysema and escape of saliva into surrounding tissue to cause infection and cellulitis. An abscess may also form. Perforation of the thoracic oesophagus may lead to mediastinitis and pleurisy.

In the cervical region a perforated oesophagus may communicate with the skin causing fistula. The wounds should be treated on general principles keeping in view the complication involved. Surgical repair of perforations and resection of fistula may be successfully done.

Esophageal fistula Esophageal fistulae may result from healing esophagotomy incisions or after esophageal perforation. They are diagnosed with contrast radiographs. Clinical signs include cervical swelling, fever, and dysphagia. Most fistulas heal once ventral drainage is established. If healing does not occur, resection of the sinus tract and closure of the stoma may be necessary.

Megaoesophagus: Sporadic reports of segmental and generalized megaoesophagus in cattle have been documented. Affected animals are dysphagic, salivate, and cough. Aspiration pneumonia is common. The esophagus is dilated on imaging studies, and the longitudinal folds of mucosa are not evident. This disorder is usually described in weanling calves that have an atonic esophagus that accumulates solid food that may occlude the esophagus and cause bloat. Regardless of age, survey radiographs reveal air or an air fluid interface within an atonic esophagus. Oesophagraphy shows a large accumulation of contrast material in the esophagus. Treatment is supportive. Animals should be frequently fed small amounts of easily digestible feeds. White muscle disease should be ruled out. Long-stemmed hay should be avoided. Antibiotics are indicated for pneumonia. The prognosis is unfavorable.